

Engaging Indonesian students in “read, reread, list, compose” strategy to enhance paraphrasing skill

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ABSTRACT

One crucial skill to master by university students related to academic writing activity is paraphrasing skill. However, in Indonesian context, the university students still find paraphrasing challenging. Therefore, this study is intended to explore the use of read, reread, list, compose (RRLC) strategy to enhance the students' paraphrasing skill in a college context. This study utilizes a qualitative case study design where the data were obtained through observation. The study revealed that RRLC stages can be implemented in learning activity. It engaged the students in activating their prior knowledge, doing an independent reading, discussing, and sharing their understanding about the text before paraphrasing. It assisted them to have better comprehension of the text to be paraphrased. In addition, during the implementation of composing stage in guided practice, the students' paraphrased works indicated that the students were able to create sentences in different structures—active or passive constructions, use the synonyms, and retain the original meaning. These three skills helped them reduce the similarity of their paraphrased works from the original version. This study recommends that RRLC strategy be implemented in teaching paraphrasing at college or lower level with some adjustments to meet the students' basic English skill.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This study attempts to investigate the English first language or EFL students' paraphrasing skills in the university context by engaging them in read, reread, list, compose (RRLC) strategy. Commonly, university students are often required to write academic work in the form of mini research, research proposal, or a thesis which can be categorized as a source-based task. Indeed, the source-based activity involves several essential writing skills such as paraphrasing skill besides higher-order thinking and reading-writing skill [1]. By paraphrasing, a writer can rewrite other's statement ideas to avoid plagiarism—one of academic violations that is firmly prohibited in the academic setting. Unfortunately, paraphrasing in foreign language is more difficult for the students than in mother tongue because of lack of experience in academic world and in technique of doing it [1]. Although a writer puts the citation clearly, lack of paraphrasing skill may lead to unintended plagiarism [2]. Thus, it is undoubtedly that academicians must have a good paraphrasing skill.

Based on the researchers' limited observation, some students at university level are still having trouble crafting effective paraphrases when they have an academic writing task. This is supported by a study done by Mori [3]. It reveals that student at undergraduate level struggle in the academic writing class,

especially in paraphrasing tasks. They find it difficult to determine proper paraphrase to be acceptable. Students' problems on making paraphrase are struggling in rearranging the structure of ideas, finding the suitable synonyms, lack of vocabularies mastery, and lack of knowledge regarding paraphrasing [4]. Those factors finally bring the students to write the original statement without paraphrasing it, which is deliberated as plagiarism. Plagiarism becomes a global problem for university students in making a writing product [5]. Plagiarism means stealing someone's idea without the author's permission and not giving credit to it [6].

The same phenomena is also found in the context of this study that is proved by students' paper similarity index that lies between 40%-25% after being checked by Turnitin. Thus, paraphrasing needs to be taught to avoid plagiarism practice [7]. This research uses RRLC including note-taking activity in writing original text as an attempt to produce a better paraphrase result and to avoid plagiarism practice. This strategy is proved to be effective in helping students paraphrase without doing plagiarism [8].

There has been some investigation on the topic of paraphrase. First, Marr [9] pinpoints that it is necessary for a writer to highlight essential parts of the original text that can assist him to produce paraphrasing with an appropriate grammatical adjustment. Second, a research by Kettel and DeFauw [8] assess the effectiveness of RRLC strategy in enhancing elementary students' paraphrasing skill. In the final result, the students were able to write a good paraphrase and avoid plagiarism practice by listing some important keywords on their notes. Last, a research by Soheim [10] evaluates the correlation study of university' English as a second language or ESL students' paraphrasing and note-taking work. As the result, there was a correlation between students' note-taking and paraphrasing skill. Given the above description, this research is different from previous studies. The first and second researches' focus are on investigating the use of paraphrasing strategies including note-taking activity in improving students' paraphrasing skill. Moreover, the third research focuses on correlation study between students' paraphrasing and note-taking ability. Meanwhile, this research emphasizes on the use of RRLC strategy in paraphrasing especially for university students.

Students in higher education level must be able to write academic works. In their academic writing process, indeed, the writers often must develop their ideas to enhance their writing. Those ideas can be obtained from various source text as their citation reference. In doing citation, it is important to have paraphrasing skill to avoid plagiarism since plagiarism is strictly prohibited in the academic environment. Unfortunately, not all citations from the source text can be considered as a proper paraphrasing. Although the writer has reconstructed the original statement grammatically, sometimes it can be considered either as good or poor paraphrase. Stawiarska in Loranc-Paszlyk [11] determines that a poor paraphrase contains less modification that consists of five or more consecutive words duplicated from the source text. This paraphrasing problem is named as a word-for-word plagiarism. Such difficulty can be prevented by providing the students with a significant integrated reading-writing tasks that make them examine and give their analysis toward the text [12]. For this reason, RRLC strategy is occupied that emphasizes on note-taking task in improving students' paraphrasing skill as proposed by Kettel and DeFauw [8]. In addition, note-taking has been studied as an effective strategy in writing activity [8], [13], [14]. It is also an applicable way to avoid plagiarism practice [8]. Olive and Barbier [14] put forward that the source text which has been formulated by note-taking degrades the cognitive effort and time consuming in reading the source text. This process also employs the function of mnemonic device to assist the students in recalling information [15].

RRLC strategy was firstly proposed by Kettel and DeFauw [8]. The strategy is intended to help the students on making acceptable paraphrase, summary, and synthesize. The use of RRLC strategy is aimed to avoid plagiarism practice by students. Kettel and DeFauw [8] proposes to conduct RRLC strategy within self-regulated strategy development (SRSD) approach. It is adaptable for any level of education and any type of writing either fiction or non-fiction texts. In addition, this strategy is adapted from the use of mnemonic devices to recall important information in which this mnemonic device is also helpful for students' planning and drafting in writing activity [16]. RRLC strategy highlights note-taking activity which is one of mnemonic devices and known as one of the effective ways in making good academic writing especially in making paraphrase [17]. Note-taking activity has been examined to give significant impact on producing good writing products [13], [18]. This RRLC strategy is conducted in four steps as its name; read, reread, list, and compose.

The first is read. Before reading, the students need to determine what types of text they have to read to fulfill their purpose of reading. This is important so the students will focus on what they need. In this step, the students read or scan the whole paragraph to make sure that their reading meets their purpose of reading. If the students have found suitable sources for their writing, they can go to the next step in this strategy. If they have not found suitable text, they can go with another text. The second is reread. Students reread the text carefully to get a deeper comprehension of the text. In the previous step, the students only focus on the main idea of the text. In this step, the students have to focus on detailed information. The third is list. After comprehending the text, the students pick certain information to be included in their writing. This

information then will be paraphrased. After the students choose certain information, they make a list of keywords from the text. The keywords should not exceed three words per row and the note should be written in their own words. The last and the fourth is compose. The students start composing the paraphrase of the chosen information. They create the paraphrase without looking at the original text. Instead, they only rely on their note of the keywords list. By looking at their list, the students will rely on their comprehension of the original text so they will avoid using copied words from the source in their paraphrase.

Conducting RRLC strategy in SRSD approach will go through the following five steps as proposed by Kettel and DeFauw [8]. First step is choosing three texts as sources. The texts are distributed for three stages, modeling, guided practice, and independent practice. The text should remain the same in the level of difficulty. Second step is informing the students about the strategy in detail including what RRLC strategy is, how it works, and what will they do during the practice. The next step is scanning one text quickly to determine whether the content of the text meets the purpose of reading. This is done to model the students. While rereading the text, make a list of keywords. The list should not exceed three words per bullet. The students can put the keywords on cards or simply on their notebook. Create the paraphrase by looking at the notes that contain list of keywords. Fourth step is continuing the guided practice, letting the students find partners to practice RRLC strategy as modeled by the teacher. This time, the students work with the second text. After the students finish their practice, encourage them to share their paraphrasing work to the class. The next step is doing an independent practice. They practice making paraphrase for the third text individually by using RRLC strategy. The last step is asking the students to share their paraphrasing work with others.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research employs a case study design of qualitative method because the aim of this research is to gain deep understanding of a phenomenon and people's subjective experience [19]. This research takes place at english education department of one state university in Bandung, West Java, Indonesia. There are nine students of the 7th semester as the participants. The students are categorized into three clusters: low, mid, and high achievers based on their achievement in the academic writing class with a number of three students for each category.

The instrument used to gather the data is observation. This is done to see the students' responses to the implementation and dialogues happened between teacher and students at the research site [20]. The observation process is conducted during the whole process of implementing read, reread, repeat, list strategy in improving students' paraphrasing skill. In this observation, the researcher takes the role as a participant-observer because the researcher is involved in the activity that is being observed. The observation is conducted two times. The first meeting covers the stages of discussing and modeling the strategy. Meanwhile, the second meeting covers the stages of guided and independent practice. According to Creswell [20], multiple observations over time will gain the best understanding of the research site and participants. Each time follows each step of regulated strategy development or SRSD approach as proposed by Rogers *et al.* [21]. They are developing background knowledge, discussing the strategy, modeling the strategy, guided practice, and individual practice respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of read, reread, list, compose or RRLC strategy covered discussing the strategy, modeling the strategy, guided practice, and independent practice stages. These stages were conducted as proposed by Kettel and DeFauw [8]. The implementation of RRLC strategy was divided into two meetings. The first meeting covered the stages of discussing and modeling the strategy. Meanwhile, the second meeting covered the stages of guided and independent practice. Both meetings were carried out through Google Meet platform. The process of each stage in implementing RRLC strategy can be seen in the following description.

3.1. Discussing the strategy

This stage was carried out in the first meeting. The teacher opened the class by mentioning the goal of the teaching which is to learn paraphrasing using RRLC strategy. The teacher also described the activities that they will get through this meeting. The teacher told the students that in the first meeting the teacher will introduce RRLC strategy and will model how to paraphrase using this strategy. Before sharing with the students what RRLC strategy is, the teacher firstly warmed up the students by asking what the students know about paraphrasing and the techniques to paraphrase. This step is also called activating background knowledge. This step is important in order that the students are connected to the materials they are going to learn. The following statement/dialogue shows the activating background knowledge.

“What do you know about paraphrasing?” (Teacher)

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“Restating someone ideas in our own words without changing the meaning (#1)” (Student DS)

“Then what techniques can be used in making paraphrase?” (Teacher)

“Change it by the synonyms (#2)” (Student DS)

“Change the grammar, such as from active to passive sentence (#3)” (Student GU)

Background knowledge has positive impact on students’ engagement in the learning activity [22], [23]. Through checking background knowledge, teachers can identify which area that the students are still lack of and get them cope with the instruction. Based on the activity, it was found that the students already had some background knowledge about paraphrasing. However, the students are still lack of knowledge of techniques in paraphrasing. The students only mentioned two kinds of technique in paraphrasing which is using the synonyms and changing the sentence structure. Therefore, the teacher mentioned five techniques in paraphrasing which is proposed by Vanitha [24] to add students’ knowledge. They are changing by synonyms, changing part of speech, changing sentence structure, reducing clauses, and mentioning the main idea or main concept. Before explaining the strategy, the teacher firstly asked the students whether they have heard or known about RRLC strategy. The students answered that they have not heard about it. The teacher then introduced RRLC strategy to the students as one of paraphrasing strategy. The following statement/dialogue shows the English teacher introduced RRLC strategy.

“So today I will introduce you to RRLC strategy. RRLC stands for Read, Reread, List, Compose. The name represents the stages that you will have to do in this strategy. The first one is Read. In this stage, you read or scan the text to get overall meaning of the text. So it is like getting the main idea. After that, we go to Reread stage. If in the previous one you only scan the text, in this stage, you read carefully to get deeper comprehension of the text. After you comprehend the text, you make a list of keywords that will be included in your paraphrase. Remember that each list should not exceed three words and please write the notes in your own words to avoid plagiarism practice. The last step is List. You start making your own paraphrase by looking at the list that you made. In making the paraphrase, try to change the sentence structure. There will be three times practice of paraphrasing using RRLC strategy. I will model the strategy at the first place. Then, there would be a practice by all of you under the guidance of the teacher. Finally, you will practice paraphrasing using RRLC strategy by yourself. (#4)” (Teacher)

While introducing RRLC strategy, the students listened closely and paid attention to the explanation. Sengsouliya *et al.* [25] state that good teaching and learning environment is essential to promote students’ engagement during the lesson. During introducing RRLC strategy, the teacher actively interacted with the students so the students were fully involved in the class. Moreover, the course of paraphrasing and steps in conducting RRLC strategy was relatable for the participants. Therefore, they actively participated during the course.

3.2. Modeling the strategy

After introducing RRLC strategy to the students, the teacher modeled how to paraphrase using RRLC strategy. The modeling strategy was intended to help the students memorize the step and transfer the strategy into their personal practice. Firstly, the teacher showed the students a text and asked them to read it together with the teacher as shown in Figure 1.

ORIGINAL TEXT
From primary schools to PhD programs, students across the globe are experiencing the altering effects of coronavirus as classrooms move online and course curriculums stretch into the summer. Both students and teachers have been burdened with the task of adapting to an online learning environment seemingly overnight. As well, many parents have been forced to take on the role of IT technician, teacher, and babysitter as kids remain stuck at home. Although the stark consequences of COVID-19 have thrown both families and the education industry for a loop, the sudden switch to digital learning has brought with it a few valuable lessons. In fact, the future of education has been transformed to not only accommodate online classrooms, but embrace a digital education.

Figure 1. Text used in modeling the strategy [26]

3.2.1. Read

In this section, the teacher, together with the students, started scanning the text to get general information on the text. One of students' problems in paraphrasing is the difficulty in comprehending the text [1]. Therefore, reading comprehension has an influential effect on paraphrasing work quality. Simanullang and Sinaga [27] found out that scanning activity has significant effect on reading comprehension. When the students and the teacher have finished reading the text, the teacher shared with the students that the general information of this text is about the effects of coronavirus on the educational field. In this section, the students also shared that they got the same information from the text as stated by the teacher. The researcher concludes that the students already have ability to scan a text. The following statement/dialogue shows the getting general information of the original text while modeling the strategy.

“So, after reading the text, I conclude that this text is about the effects of coronavirus on educational field. Do you get the same thing? (#5)” (Teacher)

“Yes, Miss” (Student)

3.2.2. Reread

The teacher split the passage into sentences to get deeper comprehension of each sentence. The teacher reread each sentence and shared with the students the meaning of it. Escudero *et al.* [28] pointed out that to make a good paraphrase needs ability of inferential thinking which is gained by a strong reading comprehension. Therefore, this step is crucial for making a paraphrase. The researcher found that it took quite long time to break each sentence and get detailed information of each phrase. For example, there were some phrases that the students did not understand the meaning. Moreover, it was harder to explain to the students to make them comprehend the sentences in detail rather than in scanning step.

3.2.3. List

After getting comprehension of each sentence, the teacher started writing notes of important keywords based on the reading as shown in Figure 2. The teacher told the students that the notes should be written in our own words and contain no more than three words in each point as suggested by Kettel and DeFauw [8] to avoid plagiarism. The researcher found that when the teacher modeled how to make the list, the students contributed their ideas in determining the keywords. However, mostly the student only changed single word by the synonym. Therefore, the teacher demonstrated that in making the list, they also can remake a phrase not a single word to avoid patchwriting practice. As Stawiarska in Loranc-Paszylik [11] stated that a good paraphrasing work is not produced by only changing with synonyms but also has inferential thinking in it.

Figure 2. Example of teacher's note of keywords adapted from RRLC strategy [8]

3.2.4. Compose

The teacher made paraphrase based on the notes that had been written while the students paid attention to it as shown in Figure 3. As written in Chen *et al.* [29], the highest level of paraphrasing work is when the paraphrase has more than one change in syntactic structure such as in adverbial position and voice. Therefore, it was emphasized that on making the paraphrase, change in the sentence structure is highlighted. It is found that it needed extra effort to demonstrate making a paraphrase while reconstructing the sentence

structure because the teacher had to get the students deal with grammatical change rules but still retaining the same meaning. However, after the teacher finished making the paraphrase and described the change in sentence structure that was applied, the students could understand it.

PARAPHRASE
 Coronavirus has affected students in any level around the world as it makes them experience online classroom and extended course. Students and teachers are required to adapt with online learning atmosphere in a short time. Moreover, as kids are staying at home, parents are urged to take multiple roles such as babysitting, mastering IT, and becoming a teacher. Despite the pandemy's effect on family and educational institution, the sudden change to online learning has actually given worth lessons. Besides accomodating online classroom, it also allows movement for the future of education into digital education.

Figure 3. Teacher's modeling paraphrasing work adapted from RRLC strategy [8]

After modeling the strategy, the teacher checked the students' understanding by doing direct questions and answers. It is found that type of questions asked by the students was more to technical issue in implementing RRLC strategy. The following statement/dialogue shows the question-and-answer session.

"Do you have any questions?" (Teacher)

"Is there any exact numbers of how many points we have to make in listing? (#6)" (Student G)

"No, there is no limitation on the number of keywords but make sure that each point has no more than three words" (Teacher)

"So, we can add conjunctions in the paraphrase? Not only arranging the keywords into sentence? (#7)" (Student F)

"Yes, the list is only the core but you can modify the sentences" (Teacher)

The students asked whether the numbers of list that have to be made is already determined and whether they can put additional function words in their paraphrase out of what they have written in their notes. The researcher found that these questions implied that the students wanted to implement RRLC strategy in proper way so the result will be better as well.

The teacher wrapped the first meeting by summarizing the lesson about RRLC strategy. The researcher found that while summarizing the lesson, the students also actively followed the teacher in recalling the lesson and got the information right. The teacher also informed the students that in the next meeting they will practice using RRLC strategy under the guidance of the teacher. The students were also informed to bring stationaries for the next meeting as they themselves will practice making a paraphrase.

In conclusion, during the first meeting, the students actively participated in the learning activity from activating background knowledge, discussing the strategy, and modeling the strategy. The students already had prior knowledge regarding paraphrasing even though they still needed some additional information about the techniques in paraphrasing. On discussing the strategy, the students were fully involved in the course due to kind of instruction and active interaction between students and teacher. Lastly, on modeling the strategy, the teacher could demonstrate the strategy to the students even though it needed extra effort and time in some steps.

3.3. Guided practice

Guided practice was conducted at the second meeting. In this meeting, the teacher let the students practice paraphrasing using RRLC strategy. Before instructing the students to practice paraphrasing using RRLC strategy, the teacher firstly informed the students about the goal and the activities that will be conducted in the second meeting. The goal of the second meeting was that the students are able to practice paraphrasing using RRLC strategy under the guidance of the teacher. The activity was continued with recalling the information about RRLC strategy that has been discussed in the previous meeting. From the recalling information activity, it is found that the students still remember the information of RRLC strategy that has been introduced in the first meeting. Cuenca *et al.* [30] pointed out that memorizing the strategy will result in fast retrieval of the infromation that should be written in the students' writing products. Therefore, the teacher can go ahead to the next activity which is guided practice. The text of guided practice is displayed in Figure 4. After showing the text, the teacher guided the students to do step by step of paraphrasing using RRLC strategy along with the teacher.

Governments can take steps now to maintain and protect the teaching force due to coronavirus. First and foremost, they need to ensure teachers continue to be paid and are positioned for a rapid school reopening once clearance is given. Second, they can make health and safety upgrades to schools, improving sanitation facilities, and guidance on issues like handwashing and health education. Finally, to make up for lost time, they can replace traditional long holidays with an extra school session.

Figure 4. Original text of guided practice [31]

3.3.1. Read

The teacher asked the students to read the whole passage and tell the teacher what it is about. After finishing reading the passage, the students told the teacher that it is about; *“Steps that can be conducted by the government to overcome coronavirus effects on educational field”*. It is found that the students can give proper main idea of the text by doing scanning activity. The following statement/dialogue shows the student’s understanding of the original text in the guided practice.

“Can you tell me what is the text about?” (Teacher)

“It is about the steps that can be conducted by the government to overcome coronavirus effects on educational field (#8)” (Student DS)

3.3.2. Reread

In this step, the text presented in Figure 4 is divided into sentences, so that it would be easier for the students to understand the message of the text as shown in Figure 5. Then, the teacher instructed the students to comprehend each sentence, for example, *“Please comprehend sentence one”*. Interaction between students and teacher is carried out during comprehending the text such as defining each vocabulary or phrase. While comprehending the text, it was found that the students faced difficulty because they did not understand some words. The students asked the teacher about words or phrases that they did not understand. Therefore, in the end the students could understand the meaning of each sentence.

Text 2: Guided Practice

1. Governments can take steps now to maintain and protect the teaching force due to coronavirus.
2. First and foremost, they need to ensure teachers continue to be paid and are positioned for a rapid school reopening once clearance is given.
3. Second, they can make health and safety upgrades to schools, improving sanitation facilities, and guidance on issues like handwashing and health education.
4. Finally, to make up for lost time, they can replace traditional long holidays with an extra school session.

Figure 5. The teacher splits the passage into sentences, adapted from RRLC strategy [8]

3.3.3. List

The teacher discussed with the students which phrases that will be included in their notes. Moreover, the synonyms of selected phrases were also discussed. The students, together with the teacher, made the list of keywords. For example, for sentence 2, they chose the phrases ‘hey’, ‘need to ensure’, ‘to be paid’, ‘school reopening’, and ‘clearance is given’. It was found that the students could determine words or phrases that would be included in their list because those that were selected were the main elements of the sentence.

3.3.4. Compose

The students begin to write the paraphrase of the selected information as displayed in Figure 6. They create the paraphrase without looking at the original text. Instead, they only rely on their knowledge of the keyword list. By looking at their list, the students will rely on their comprehension of the original text, so they will avoid using copied words from the source in their paraphrase. A change in the sentence structure was also emphasized to the students. However, they were authorized to explore their preferences in arranging the sentences.

First and foremost, they need to ensure teachers continue to be paid and are positioned for a rapid school reopening once clearance is given.

- Need to ensure/ guarantee
- They/ government
- To be paid/ getting salary
- Clearance is given/ pandemy is over

1. The teacher salary must be guaranteed and when the pandemy is over they must do reopening school. (Rev)

2. When the pandemy is over, they must reopen the school and guarantee the teachers' salary.

Figure 6. Example of students guided paraphrasing practice, adapted from RRLC strategy [8]

Figure 6 shows a student's paraphrasing work that was shared with the teacher and friends. It was shown that the students created the sentence in different structure, used the synonyms, and retained the original meaning. In the original text, the sentence was written in active voice while in the student's paraphrasing work, the sentence was written in passive voice. Moreover, the student changed some words with the synonyms. For example, the word 'ensure' was replaced by 'guarantee'. The original text and the student's paraphrasing work also have the same meaning that state "the government's obligation to pay the teachers and open the school once the pandemic is over". The revised version is written when the teacher gave feedback to students' work and gave alternatives on how to arrange the paraphrase.

3.4. Independent practice

The task for independent practice as revealed in Figure 7 was distributed to the students at the end of second meeting through Whatsapp group chat. Based on the data gained from observation, all stages were conducted during implementing the strategy. The implementation of RRLC strategy was conducted in Self-Regulated learning as proposed by Kettel and DeFauw [8]. They were discussing the strategy, modeling the strategy, guided practice, and independent practice. In addition, the students' works show that the RRLC strategy helps the students to practice using synonymous words more frequently in appropriate manner (for high and mid achieving students) and some are inappropriate usage of synonym for low achieving students. Moreover, more syntactic changes are also made by high and mid achieving students.

Text 3: Independent Practice

Instruction: Please paraphrase the passage below!

Families who already feel an economic squeeze from the COVID-19 outbreak may not be able to budget the hundreds of dollars necessary for college acceptance deposits. They also might need to rely on their children as an additional source of income, which could prevent some young people from attending college at all. School closures also have separated students from teachers, counselors, and other staff members who can support them during important developmental transitions. In addition, many students will be asked to balance their own needs with those of their younger siblings, becoming at-home caregivers for families who don't have another option.

Figure 7. Task for independent practice [32]

Before discussing the strategy, the students showed that they had prior knowledge about paraphrasing as they learned in Academic Writing class in the 5th semester but they did not have any prior knowledge about RRLC strategy. However, additional information was delivered by the instructor to make the students easier to cope with the next activities. Rogers *et al.* [21] proposes that activating background knowledge is very important to determine the beginning instruction and treat the students based on their prior knowledge and ability. All information about RRLC strategy as stated by Kettel and DeFauw [8] was informed to the students. All steps including read, reread, list, and compose steps were also demonstrated to make the students understand RRLC strategy better. The students also actively participated during the course by interactively communicated with the teacher. The students' involvement during the course was caused by the kind of course and teacher's behavior [25].

Before conducting guided practice, students' comprehension of the strategy was checked because Escudero [28] stated that reading comprehension influences paraphrasing quality. The students showed that they had good comprehension of RRLC strategy. The result of the practice also showed that they can produce good paraphrasing work under the guidance of the instructor. The assistant of the teacher might contribute to the result as the students said that they were facing difficulties in understanding the original text. As stated in research by Na and Mai [1], one of students' difficulties in producing paraphrase is that face difficulty in understanding the source text. However, as the instructor guided them, it was easier for them to comprehend the text.

After implementing RRLC strategy, it can be concluded that this strategy is advantageous to teach students how to do paraphrasing without doing plagiarism practice. This is because this strategy contains steps where the students are directly instructed to avoid plagiarism practice by changing the keywords into their own words. However, the teacher also needs to pay attention to other factors such as reading comprehension skill and vocabulary mastery because those factors play important role in making paraphrase using this strategy. Na and Mai [1] also found that reading comprehension skill and vocabulary mastery obstruct the students to make good paraphrase. Therefore, mastering those skill is needed in advance before learning to paraphrase using RRLC strategy.

4. CONCLUSION

The implementation of read, reread, list, compose (RRLC) strategy helps the students paraphrase the text more easily, since the strategy provides clear steps to be followed by students: read, reread, list, and compose. To implement this, teachers need to consider the students' prior skills including comprehension skill, vocabulary and grammatical mastery. Without one of these prior skills, the students may still be able to paraphrase. However, both teachers and students may find it still challenging to produce good paraphrased works. Among the three prior skills, comprehension skill plays the most major role that determines the quality of paraphrased works, because understanding of the content guarantees the accuracy of the content of the paraphrased works. In short, this RRLC strategy seems to be effective to be implemented in different levels of education: secondary to tertiary level.

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